

A spatial framework to identify bright spots and structural gaps for the development of sociobiodiversity bioeconomy: evidence from the Brazilian Cerrado

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Material 1

Figure S1 – Original data used to estimate potential areas for traditional NTFP use. (A) average historical production of NTFPs (1986 to 2023), (B) NTFPs 2023 Simpson's diversity index, (C) UCs of sustainable use (e.g., environmental protection area, national forest, state forest, extractive reserve, sustainable

development reserve) with indigenous lands and rural settlements, (D) quilombola areas, (E) isolated rural agglomeration and (F) fragments of native vegetation (forests and savannah).

Random Forest Mean Squared Error: 0.004873532704610042

Feature Importance Scores:

	Feature	Importance
4	veg_nativa	0.521697
2	quilombola	0.196689
0	div_2023	0.145068
3	vilarejo	0.070577
1	areas_protegidas	0.065969

Figure S2 - Random Forest model and Feature Importance Scores in correlation analysis in section 2.1.1.

Figure S3 - Deforestation caused by soy and pasture intensification original data used in correlation analysis in section 2.1.1.

Figure S4 – Spatial explicit distribution of (A) HDI and (B) SVI. Both original data used in correlation analysis in section 2.1.1.

Figure S5 – Correlation matrix in section 2.1.1.

Supplementary Material 2

Figure S6 – Original database of intermediary actors (A) NGOs, institutes and foundations, cooperatives and associations and APL from ISA, CEPF-Cerrado, Fundo Ecos, IPEA, WWF, ICMBio, FUNBIO, RHISA and CONEXUS. Functions/roles of intermediary actors: (B) Advocacy and Rights, (C) Capacity Building, (D) Environmental Conservation, (E) Market access and (F) Production Support.

Figure 7 – (A) Number of actors (actors' richness), by counting the number of intermediary actors (e.g., cooperatives, associations, NGOs) within each of the 1,434 municipalities within Cerrado. (B) diversity of the functions that characterize their management capabilities (actors' functional diversity).

Supplementary Material 3

Figure 8 – Original data for (A) road infrastructure (transport), (B) energy, (C) digital communications and (D) water management.

Supplementary Material 4

Figure 9 - “Elbow point” method (where the rate of WCSS reduction slows down) suggests a suitable cluster count for K-means algorithm.